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Talents in Vocational Education

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Abstract

Talent is an international research topic, but the definition of talent, how to spot talent and measurements of talent development are discussed. This study in talent in Danish vocational educations is based on a documentary study analyses the development of policy. It shows that three phases can be identified where the definition of talent change. Based on five reports, the knowledge of talent is analysed using the categories definition of talent, criteria in spotting talent, domains, developments of talent. It is concluded that projects and research interest in the qualitative based studies are changing over time, and since different terms are used, a comparison is complicated. However, teaching, pedagogic and didactic seems as important for talents and talent development as for other groups of students.

Keywords

giftedness; talent, talent development; vocational education; policy

1 Introduction

In Danish vocational educations and policy in general talent is at the agenda (e.g. Nissen et al., 2011; Government, 2014). However, talent is not easy to define or to measure. In the international literature, giftedness and talent are defined in four different ways leaning on a "psychometric definitions, performance definitions, labelling definitions and specific giftedness/talent definitions" and "There is no generally accepted understanding of the difference between the two" (Stroeger et al., 2018, p. 25). Furthermore, it is difficult to distinguish between a personality trait and a probability for the future outcome. Later research includes "personality traits such as creativity or motivation" and include context, learning processes and agents in the context (Stroeger et al., 2018, p. 26). The approaches to talent are influenced by culture, e.g. gifted and identification of those that are dominant in western journals from 2009-2015 (Stroeger et al., 2018, p. 29). Identification of talent or giftedness can be "status oriented, intervention oriented, development oriented and support oriented" (Stroeger et al., 2018, p. 30). Unfortunately, the research in talented programs is sparse. Some programs involve "curriculum acceleration and enrichment", and other programs include "differentiation and grouping practices" (Stroeger et al., 2018 p. 31). Research in secondary school and upper secondary school show sociologically related problems and issues in programs (Rasmussen, 2012; Rasmussen & Rasmussen, 2015; Rasmussen & Lingard, 2018).

In the research area of giftedness and talent, many models are made (Gagné, 2004; 2010; Stroeger et al., 2018). Looking at vocational educations Nokelainen and Polyväs have made an

empirically and theoretically- based model integrating both the context at school and workplace (Pylvä & Nokelainen, 2017) and more research is done in the context of Finland (Pylväs et al., 2018). This model distinguishes between gifts and talents. Gifts are natural abilities related to intelligence, and the approach is building on Howard Gardner's multiple intelligence. Talents are "the process of how inborn gifts develop into talents" (Pylvä & Nokelainen, 2017, p. 98). The student has some intrinsic characteristics. Based on Albert Bandura's psychological theory, these characteristics include motivation, volition and self-reflection. The student also has some extrinsic conditions. Some are related to parents, e.g. "make the talent field accessible and desirable to their children", and some are related to friends (Pylvä & Nokelainen, 2017, p. 101). Other extrinsic conditions are directly related to the school. These conditions are called domain-specific conditions and are artefacts, teachers, trainers and coo workers. The integrations of such conditions relate to a socio-cultural understanding, e.g. by theorist as Jean Lave and Etienne Wenger (1991).

The purpose of this short paper is to contribute to the research in talent by presenting Danish vocational educations as a case. I am asking how policy addresses talent, and what knowledge exists from research. Since research is sparse, development projects are also included.

2 Methods

Policy documents about talent are collected using snowballing (Lynggaard, 2015). This documentation includes papers and reports made by expert groups with members selected by the political system to make recommendations for future policy. These documents also include quantitative data from 2016, 2017 and 2018, counting the number of talents (National Agency for IT and learning, 2019). This material is analysed, and based on this analysis, a brief overview of the historical development is made.

Furthermore, research articles are located. Two Danish peer-reviewed research articles concern the topic of talents in vocational educations (Christensen, 2015; 2016). Christensen is using an ethnographic approach. She raises a pedagogical debate discussing if the focus of talent is prioritising, e.g. combating at skills instead of building the students identity as a professional. Such discussions can be seen as contributing to the research in the reforms of Danish VET (e.g. Jørgensen, 2016; Hjort-Madsen, 2016). Documents about talent are found at webpages from the two prominent university colleges in Denmark. This search shows five reports categorised as evaluation or as research of initiatives and projects about defining talent, talent spotting and developing talent. Three of the documents are from 2015 (Allermand et al., 2015; Gleerup et al., 2015; Teknologisk Institut; 2015), and two documents are from 2018 (Iversen et al., 2018; Rambøll, 2018a). There are other documents concerning the same reports, but they are background papers, working papers or suggestions to teachers and managers (e.g. Nistrup & Larsen, 2015; Ministry of Education, 2018; Rambøll, 2018b; Talentvejen; 2019).

The documents are analysed (Prior, 2011) using categories from the model made by Pylvä & Nokelainen (2017). These categories are extrinsic conditions that are domain specific such as levels and courses, access to technology, teachers, workplace and skills. Systematic development of vocational skills in different skill arenas – in the workplace or at school by pedagogy and didactic – are categories. The categories are also a definition of talent and criteria for talent spotting such as intelligence, motivation, self-regulation and volition. The choice and further development of categories are based on the first phase of the analyses. Thereafter the documents are analysed more systematically. The categories are shown in the figure below (Table 1).

In the next paragraphs, the analyses will be presented. First, is the analysis of the talent policy in Danish VET and then the analysis of the knowledge from projects at VET.

Table 1
Categories used in analyses of documents

Definition of talent	
Criteria in talent spotting	Intelligence, e.g. by using grades
	Motivation
	Self-regulation
	Volition
Domains	Levels of course
	Access to technology
	Teachers
	Work-place
	Skills
Development of talent	Pedagogy and didactic at school
	Workplace

3 Talent policy in Danish VET

Talents have been on the political agenda in Denmark for a longer period since at least 1989. There have been different kinds of competitions, including skills competitions (Ministry of Education, 2008b; SkillsDenmark, 2019). In 2004, the Ministry of Education initiated a working group, and this starts - what I will call - the first phase of talent policy (Ministry of Education, 2008b). The argumentation for the policy is based on the global competition. At this stage, the definition of talent is "a person, that is good at something and have the possibility to increase this potential if stimulated [my translation] (Ministry of Education, 2008b). The psychologist Kyed argues with references to the national economy and ethical obligations to support people's development (Kyed, 2005). He argues that talent spotting is important to ensure stimulation of talents in the context. Such issues are discussed, as well as the definition of talent in 2005 (Uddannelse, 2005). In the period 2006 to 2008, the Ministry of Education finances two projects at vocational colleges (Ministry of Education, 2008a). The policy is trying to change the attitude to talent and talent development (Ministry of Education, 2008b; EVA, 2011). This goal implies the improvement of access to further education and participating in skills, which are national and international competing in vocations and vocational colleges (Uddannelse, 2005; Ministry of Education, 2008b).

The next phase of talent policy begins in 2010. As in 2004 Ministry of Education initiates a working group and their paper is renewing the policy (Hermann et al., 2011). With this phase, the definition of talent change. "Talent is not only the young who can and will. Talent is also young that maybe can and who have the will to work for the expansion of their talent" [my translation] (Hermann et al., 2011, p. 12). This definition is broader than the description from 2008 as quoted above. The working group recommends a so-called 'talent track' at vocational colleges. It is also recommended that teachers are taught a 'talent didactic' at compulsory teacher education (Nistrup & Larsen, 2015). An evaluation from 2011 states that there is now awareness of the 'strong students' at the colleges. This emphasis is a change from plenty of initiatives on the 'weak students' (EVA, 2011).

From 2015 a reform of vocational colleges is implemented (Government et al., 2014). In this reform, the talent track is realised. Data shows that the percentage of students on the talent track are slightly declining over the years when this program is running (Figure 1).

Figure 1*Percentage of all students in talent track*

Legend. National Agency for IT and learning (2019)

In 2019, the Minister of Education initiated a new initiative, and a third phase starts (Ministry of Education, 2019). The initiative is debated in parliament, but later part of it is withdrawn without thorough explanations. In the debate, the opposition asked questions about how to identify and motivate talents and accommodate the rest of the students (Finansudvalget, 2019). The opposition also asked about how to avoid stress pressing on pupils. That concern was in the general educational debate at that time. These topics can indicate that talent and, e.g. equality in educations are important political questions. In 2019, also a new order called 'the talent order' [my translation] is resolved (Ministry of Higher Education and Science, 2019). This approach allows youth from vocational educations to take subjects at a higher level in further education without having attained the admission demands for formal qualifications. It can be interpreted as if the talent tracks mentioned above are substituted for such initiatives. Newly established knowledge centers complement the work with talents at vocational colleges. The centers must have talent tracks for students at vocational colleges, but it might be difficult to make student attend (e.g. Talents of Retail, 2019).

Summing up, the policy can be divided into three phases. The first two are linked to a working group with experts who defines talent. This definition is changing over the stages. The third phase starts with policy initiatives at a ministry and is partly withdrawn again; however, there is one significant change. Students from youth educations can attend courses from higher education, and talent tracks seem to be moved from vocational education in general to knowledge centres working nation-wide. In the next paragraph, the analyses of knowledge from different projects at VET will be presented.

4 Knowledge from projects at VET

Three of the reports concerning talent are published in 2015 and two in 2018. Therefore, all of them are initiated in the second phase of the talent policy as it is defined above. However, it is the reform of the Danish VET in 2015 that, among other things, introduced talent track. This introduction was a recommendation from the beginning of phase two. Figure 2 shows the phases of policy, the timeline for the reform and the analysed documents.

Figure 2

Phases of the talent policy, the documents about talent and the VET reform.

The documents published in 2015 are based on projects running from 2010 to 2015. They will be presented below, one at the time.

The first document is 'Talent development' [my translation]. The study is called a case study involving three vocational colleges (Allermann et al., 2015). The study defines talent as 10-20% of proficient students. These students are characterised by cleverness and persistence. They also have good cognitive competence, self-motivation and innovative competences. Criteria for spotting talents are professional ability, persistence, being interested, creativity, concentration, responsible, having a big overview and that they can cooperate. In some of the cases, tests are used in spotting talent. Summing up, the definition of talent and the criteria in spotting are very open and wide. The domains in the study are students attending the highest possible level of courses and access to relevant equipment such as technology.

Furthermore, the teaching is mentioned as a domain: teachers have to guide, express equality between teacher and student, have high professional capital and good education and teachers have to be well qualified. In addition, the skills from innovation camp are mentioned. This means that the domains included in this study are broad. Talent development in this document includes pedagogic and didactic at college and internship abroad. Overall, the document shows a study that includes:

Definition of talent

Spotting talent

Domains: level of courses, access to technology, teaching and skills

Talent development: pedagogic and didactic, workplace

The next document is summarising research in a report called 'talent spotting' [my translation] (Gleerup et al., 2015). Talent is called a fluent signifier combining natural gifts and learned abilities. The criteria for talent spotting are diligence, capacity, engagement, independence, experience, motivation, empathy, innovations. Adding competencies as analytical, imagination, knowing the material and creating results. This research also includes the domain of teaching, pointing out that teacher development is important. Talent development is connected to pedagogic and didactic issues, including being goal oriented, differentiating, giving feedback, planning, and methods. Furthermore, the involvement of knowledge, and observations of students, and teachers who need the ability to talk about and have a vocabulary to discuss pedagogic and didactic concerns are also mentioned. The students' personal development is important, but the distance is also needed. This study includes:

Definition of talent

Spotting talent

Domains: level of courses, teaching, workplace

Talent development: pedagogic and didactic, personal development

Compared to the first-mentioned study, the similarity is that these four categories are included, although there are some variations in the focus. However, the analyses show a change in the forthcoming reports.

The document 'Road to talent' is called an evaluation [my translation] (Teknologisk Institut, 2015). Talents are selected as being included in the best 10%. The criteria for talent spotting are volition, engagement, curiosity, social competences, innovative and overview. Three domains include levels of courses, teaching and workplace, but more important are talent development. It is said that talent development should be integrated everywhere, and this can include talent teams in shorter periods. The report mentions a didactic for talent development and personal development of students that provides for motivation and self-confidence. Overall, the document shows a study that includes:

Definition of talent
Spotting talent
Domains: levels of courses, teaching, workplace
Talent development: pedagogic and didactic, personal development

4.1 Documents from 2018

The document 'talent development' [my translation] defines talents as students on the talent track (Iversen et al., 2018). The research report presents 12 cases for students at internship; therefore, the main domain is the workplace. The researchers write that they assume that identity as becoming a skilled worker is important. They mention coherence between vocational college and internship, and they highlight progression in learning, organisation, role models and relations. Talent development at the workplace is related to the students' dispositions, tasks, interactions, credit and dialogue. Therefore, this document is about:

Domain: workplace
Talent development: workplace

The last document, 'talent track and subjects at higher levels' [my translation], is closely connected to the VET reform and can be understood as an intervention to implement this reform (Rambøll, 2018a). The domain is teaching, interpreting and implementing the reform. Talent development at workplaces is mentioned reminding the importance of the dialogues between the central agents involved in talent track. However, talent development as pedagogic and didactic at college are the main focus. Talent development can attract more students. Students need help to motivation to chose talent track and subjects at higher levels than are compulsory, and teachers have to implement the reform, develop their teaching, including differentiated instruction. So, the categories involved are the domain of teaching and talent development as pedagogic and didactic groupings that include the workplace.

5 Conclusion

This short paper shows the policy chance of talent showing shifts in 2005, 2010 and 2019. The definition of talent chance and this influences the vocational educations, but a major change relates to the VET reform in 2015 integrating the recommendation of talent track. The documents that are found relates to phase two. Three documents are from 2015 that is before the VET reform is implemented. Two documents are from 2018 – after the reform. Figure 2 illustrates this. Since the documents use different terminology, it can be complicated to compare them. Even when the same terms are used, it can be related to different understandings. Because the reports are not associated with theoretical approaches, the positions are not always entirely

clear. However, using the model made by Pylvä and Nokelainen (2017) provides categories that can systematise the reading of the documents.

Comparing the documents there seems to be a slight shift from interest in the definition of talent and talent spotting to talent development. This issue can be related to the VET reform since the definition of talent is defined as being in talent track. The discussion of the meaning of talent and talent spotting seems thereby minimised. Only one document has the main focus on internship and the conditions, relations etc. in the workplace. Pedagogy and didactic methods in the vocational colleges are mentioned in four of the documents, but the approaches are very broad. The theoretical understandings are not explicated and, therefore, it is difficult to point out things in common. Based on this research, we conclude that knowledge of talent at VET in Denmark is sparse. However, each document contributes to showing the complexity of talent at VET. The model made by Pylvä and Nokelainen (2017) give categories that need further exploration.

Since talent and talent spotting is very open defined, it can be challenging to work with at the vocational colleges. The discussion of the definition of talent was less important by using talent track as a definition, but this did not make any increase in the counted numbers of talents.

Since knowledge of talent at VET must be found in qualitative studies using different methodologies and very broad definitions and terminology, summing up the knowledge is difficult even as the model and categories in use make it possible to make a kind of comparison and conclusion.

Teaching and pedagogic and didactic issues are addressed in the documents, but it could be discussed how and if this concern is special to talents. This discussion might address not only talents but also all other students. So maybe talented and gifted students at VET can gain from initiatives intended for other groups of students as well. The main questions might still relate to the learning and development of all students at the VET.

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